

Training and Development Analysis of Individual Behaviour, IT Industry Employees in Chennai City

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Abstract: The article tries to finding out philosophical perspective of training and development analysis of individual behavior among IT employees in Chennai City. One objective of this study is reached through proper methodology. Sample size was 840 in all obtained through convenience sampling technique in Chennai city, Tamilnadu, India. Researcher designed questionnaire is with 5 point scale in the continuum of agreeing. Reliability of this tool is 0.87 and 0.90. Multiple group path analysis was used for data analysis.

I Introduction

Training and development refers to the imparting of specific skills, abilities and knowledge to an employee. A formal definition of training & development is... it is any attempt to improve current or future employee performance by increasing an employee's ability to perform through learning, usually by changing the employee's attitude or increasing his or her skills and knowledge. The fundamental aim of training is to help the organization achieve its purpose by adding value to its key resource – the people it employs. Training means investing in the people to enable them to perform better and to empower them to make the best use of their natural abilities. The particular objectives of training are to:

- Develop the competences of employees and improve their performance;
- Help people to grow within the organization in order that, as far as possible, its future needs for human resource can be met from within;
- Reduce the learning time for employees starting in new jobs on appointment, transfers or promotion, and ensure that they become fully competent as quickly and economically as possible.

II Review of Literature

According to Chhokra, Bhanu (2015) Training and Development is an indispensable function in an ever changing and fast paced corporate world but most of the companies pay least importance to it. Ganesh, M., Indradevi R., (2015), Training and Development plays an important role in the effectiveness of organizations and to make people to do work effectively & efficiently. It is said that training has implications on Productivity, commitment to the work and personal development. All

companies must train people and develop their staff. Most of the organizations are aware of this requirement and invest and do many things for training and development. Velmurugan P. S., (2009) Training is the periscope to see the future. It is intended to identify the future of the organization to develop and steer them. Development creates generalists and helps people to think strategically, even when their present jobs do not call for such thinking. It pushes and stretches people beyond their present function. Khan, Abdul Ghafoor, Khan, Furqan Ahmed, Khan, Muhammad Aslam Khan (2011), Training and Development, On the Job Training, Training Design and Delivery style are four of the most important aspects in organizational studies. This paper tried to evaluate the effect of Training and Development, On the Job Training, Training Design and Delivery style on Organizational performance. Swaminathan, J. and Gowri Shankar, U., (2011). This paper tries to conclude that training is the act of increasing the knowledge and skill of an employee for doing a particular job. The training is to acquire new skill, technical knowledge, problem solving, etc. It improves the performance of employees on present jobs and prepares them for taking up new assignments in the future. Training also helps in the growth of the employees. The main objective of the study is to measure the effectiveness of the training in the organization and its impact on employee job performance. Chris Obisi (2011) The ultimate aim of any training program is to add value and once a training program cannot add value, it should be reworked or altogether revoked. Acquisition of new skills is only possible with Training Programs and without skills organizations will not achieve its objectives through people. Some organizations see training as an expensive venture and may put embargo on training and utilize the money for other projects in the organization. Scott Brum, University Of Rhode Island (2007) To gain an advantage amongst competitors training is of great importance to companies. There is significant debate among professionals and scholars as to the affect that training has on both employee and organizational goals. Chidambaram, Vijayabanu I, Ramachandran, Amudha (2012) The success of any organization depends on appropriate use of human assets available in the organization. All other assets could only be supplementary to human assets. Towards augmenting the human resources and to cope with changes – both internal and external, the organization has to concentrate necessarily on developing the ability, wisdom and skills of its workforce which is possible through training programs. Aidah Nassazi (2013) According to this study “effects of training on employee performance.” Employees are major assets of any organization. The active role they play towards a company’s success cannot be underestimated. As a result, equipping these unique assets through effective training becomes imperative in order to maximize the job performance. Bhatia et al., (2014), Training is a medium to bring continuous improvement in the Performance analysis of work performed; it would equip employees with necessary knowledge, skill, abilities and attitude to perform their jobs. B.K. Punia, Saurabh Kant (2014) the authors tried to depict the importance of factors affecting training effectiveness vis-à-vis managerial implications and future research directions The findings of this study suggest many factors which affects training effectiveness like motivation, attitude, emotional intelligence, support from management and peers, training style and environment, open-mindedness of trainer, job related factors, self efficacy and basic ability etc. Ambika Bhatia & Lovleen Kaur (2014) In today’s era employees are not keen to join an organization where their Knowledge and skills are not upgraded. Many organizations provide opportunities for learning and use it as a retention tool. Results prove that training and development are positively correlated and claimed significant statistical relationship with employee performance and effectiveness.

A Framework of the Study

Figure 1: Framework

This study adopts only three common independent variables namely person analysis, work analysis and performance analysis. It was planned to assure how these factors relate within themselves and influence the Productivity.

B Statement of the Problem

In today's era, Organizations operate in a continuous learning mode because of high competition in the market. The organizations and individuals should show flexibility in becoming continuous learner in order to survive & develop, which would further help companies to become most successful. In an association, the most vital task is to put the right person at the right place, otherwise companies would only keep on trying to survive in the competitive world. Majority times the lack of motivation on part of the individuals accompanied with lack of knowledge of the specific job can lead to grievous situations and a big loss to companies. Hence there is no doubt on the importance of continuous upgrade and training in the relevant domains to cope up with the competitive strategies in the market. There is a continuous need to ensure effective training to match up with such market requirements not to be the best but most importantly for the necessary survival. The primary objective of this paper is to conduct a comprehensive study and analysis of training and development process of IT Companies which would be helpful in highlighting the importance of discovering, harnessing and developing the human capital to the benefit of both the individual and the organization in today's highly dynamic and competitive business world, having a special reference for managerial position. Thus the sample comprised of IT employees who were of manager rank and above.

III Research Methodology

A Research Design

To obtain better answer to the research question, a proper research design is to be framed (Cooper & Schindler 2001; Davis & Cosenza 1988). Based on the framed hypotheses of the research inferential statistics was adopted. Descriptive research design was adopted in this study.

B Objective of the study

- Finding out those factors which Promote Productivity.

C Hypotheses of the study

- There is no influence of person analysis with respect to gender of the employees.
- There is no influence of work analysis with respect to gender of the employees.
- There is no influence of performance analysis with respect to gender of the employees.
- There is no influence of personal analysis on opinion towards T and D with respect to gender of the employees.

D Scope of the Study

Scope of the study is as follows

- The study is centered at Chennai city only.

➤ Study is related only with personal analysis of training and development.

E Data Collection

Under this technique convenience sampling technique was opted. Sample size was 840. The sampling area was Chennai city.

F Reliability

For all the items in the self questionnaire design, the alpha values ranged from 0.87 and 0.90. This indicates high reliability of the items in the questionnaire. With these results, consistency, dependability and adoptability are confirmed.

G Period of the study

The study was carried from the Chennai city between the periods of Aug 2020to April 2021.

H Tool for data analysis

Path analysis was adopted for primary data analysis. Influence of independent variables on dependent variable with respect to mediator variables.

IV Analysis and Discussion

Table 1: Demographic profile

S.No	Profile	Category	No. of Employees	Percent
1.	Gender	Male	472	56.20
		Female	368	43.80
		Total	840	100.00
2.	Age	Up to 30 Years	392	46.60
		31 to 45 Years	245	29.20
		Above 45 Years	203	24.20
		Total	840	100.00
3.	Income	Up to 25000	198	23.57
		25001 to 50000	282	33.57
		Above 50000	360	42.86
		Total	840	100.00

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the demographic profile of the employees. Regarding to gender of the employees, 56.2 percent of the employees are male and remaining are female employees. With regard to age of the employees, 46.6 percent comes under up to 30 years, 29.2 percent comes under 31 to 45 years and remaining employees comes under above 45 years of age groups. With respect to income of the employees, 23.57 percent earned up to 25000, 33.57 percent earned 25001 to 50000 and remaining employees earned above 50000.

Path Analysis

Table 1: Model fit Indication

X ²	P	GFI	AGFI	CFI	NFI	RMSEA	RMS
2.326	0.084	0.999	0.982	0.999	0.999	0.001	0.024

Source: primary data

Table 1 shows the model summary. While evaluating the model, emphasis is to be given to the chi-square value and the p-value. The p-value of the corresponding chi-square should be greater than 0.05. Then only the model fits to the data collected for the analysis. It does not mean it is not totally fit. Secondly other indices are to be considered which are expected to be very near to 'one'. In this path analysis GFI is .988; AGFI is .942; CFI is .991 and NFI is .987 all these values are very near to 'one'; hence it can be interpreted that the model is fit with the theoretical model and the data collected and related to it. Thirdly RMSEA should be below .08; In this study it is .06 only; hence it proves that the model is fit.

The technique of the path analysis is based on series of multiple regression analysis with the assumption of casual relationship between the independent and the dependent variables. In the path analysis β coefficient indicates the direct effect of independent variables over the dependent variables. Path analysis adopts heuristic use of visual diagrams. Multiple group path analysis is adopted to find out the significant differences between the responses of two or more group using the same model fit.

Path analysis diagram related to male

Figure 2: Productivity – Gender – Male

Table 2: Regression Weights of Productivity of Male Employees

DV		IV	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	B	p
T & D	<~	Personal analysis	0.420	0.040	10.404	0.359	0.001
T & D	<~	Work analysis	0.288	0.027	10.501	0.376	0.001
T & D	<~	Performance analysis	0.100	0.033	3.054	0.102	0.002
Productivity	<~	T & D	0.934	0.064	14.632	0.520	0.001

Source: primary data

Table 3: Covariance Productivity of Male Employees

IV		IV	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	R	p
Work analysis	<->	Performance analysis	3.536	0.656	5.390	0.230	0.001
Work analysis	<->	Personal analysis	8.077	1.032	7.829	0.345	0.001
Performance analysis	<->	Personal analysis	8.084	0.882	9.161	0.413	0.001

Source: primary data

From the path analysis diagram related to male, one can note some readings about the relationships and the influences of them over the dependent variables. It is established that the relationship between Performance analysis and Personal analysis is 0.413. The correlation value for Personal analysis and Work analysis is 0.345 and that of Work analysis and Performance analysis seems to be 0.23. All these readings show the relationships among the independent variables; all these readings indicate the average relationships among these and are positively correlated.

The influence of Work analysis over the T & D remains as 0.376 and is the highest of all the influences; Personal analysis influence is 0.359 and the Performance analysis influence over the T & D is 0.102; hence it can be inferred that the Work analysis is the factor which contribute to the T & D thereby it is well understood that the Productivity is well understood that the Productivity is promoted by the Work analysis and less influenced by the Work analysis and less influenced by Personal analysis and Performance analysis. The influence of T & D over Productivity is 0.520 and is positive as far as male are concerned. R² for the T & D is 0.44 and that of Productivity is 0.27; it can be stated that the consolidated influences of the Personal analysis, Work analysis and Performance analysis over the T & D specifically renders 44 percent of influencing effect over the Productivity. Baek, (2010), Grisaffe and Nguyen, (2011) and Bartikowski, *et al.* (2010) they also found that influence of the Personal analysis, Work analysis, Performance analysis and T & D on Productivity.

The regression weights of the male responses are shown in the table 2. The table shows the effects of independent variables Personal analysis, Work analysis and Performance analysis toward the Productivity through the T & D which is the mediating dependent variable.

The independent variable Personal analysis shows the estimate as 0.420; SE as 0.040; CR as 10.404 towards T & D which is the mediating dependent variable. The B- value is 0.359 and its corresponding p- value is 0.001 which means that the independent variable Personal analysis influence the Productivity through the mediator dependent variable T & D to 35.9 per cent. The Personal analysis shows significant influence over the mediating dependent variable T & D. So there is influence of Personal analysis on T & D.

The independent variable Work analysis shows the estimate as 0.288; SE as 0.027; CR as 10.501 towards T & D which is the mediating dependent variable. The B- value is 0.376 and its corresponding p- value is 0.000 which means that the independent variable Work analysis influence the Productivity through the mediator dependent variable T & D to 37.6 percent. The Work analysis shows significant influence over the mediating dependent variable T & D. So there is influence of Work analysis on T & D.

The independent variable Performance analysis shows the estimate as 0.100; SE as 0.033; CR as 3.054 towards T & D which is the mediating dependent variable. The B- value is 0.102 and its corresponding p- value is 0.015 which means that the independent variable Performance analysis influence the Productivity through the mediator dependent variable T & D to 10.2 percent. The

Performance analysis shows significant influence over the mediating dependent variable T & D. There is influence of Performance analysis on T & D.

The mediating dependent variable T & D shows the estimate as 0.934; SE as 0.064; CR as 14.632 towards T & D which is the mediating dependent variable. The B- value is 0.520 and its corresponding p- value is 0.000 which means that the mediator dependent variable T & D, influence the Productivity through the mediator dependent variable T & D to 52 percent. The T & D shows significant influence over the main dependent variable Productivity.

The following table jot out the covariance of the responses of the male. The covariance of male among the independent variables of the study shows the following details. The independent variables namely Personal analysis, Work analysis and Performance analysis have their own interrelationships. The relationship of Work analysis and Performance analysis shows the estimate as 3.536 with the SE of 0.656, the critical ratio is 5.390 and the coefficient of correlation is 0.230 and is positive. Since the p- value is 0.000 it is significant; it can be interpreted that the Work analysis and Performance analysis are significantly related with each other. The relationship of Work analysis and Personal analysis shows the estimate as 8.077 with the SE of 1.032, the critical ratio is 7.829 and the coefficient of correlation is 0.345 and is positive. Since the p-value is 0.000 it is significant; it can be interpreted that the Work analysis and Personal analysis are significantly related with each other.

The relationship of Performance analysis and Personal analysis shows the estimate as 8.084 with the SE of 0.882, the critical ratio is 9.161 and the coefficient of correlation is 0.413 and is positive. Since the p-value is 0.000 it is significant; it can be interpreted that the Work analysis and Performance analysis are significantly related with each other.

With the readings it can be understood that all the three dependent variables namely Work analysis, Personal analysis and Performance analysis are correlated positively and significantly.

Path analysis diagram related to female

Table 4: Regression Weights of Productivity of Female Employees

DV		IV	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	B	p
T & D		Personal analysis	0.287	0.088	3.271	0.241	0.001
T & D		Work analysis	0.269	0.057	4.706	0.359	0.001
T & D		Performance analysis	0.113	0.075	2.807	0.121	0.007
Productivity		T & D	0.915	0.141	6.504	0.467	0.001

Source: primary data

Productivity – Gender – Female

Figure 3: Productivity – Gender – Female

Table 5: Covariance of Productivity of Female Employees

IV		IV	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	R	p
Work analysis	<-->	Performance analysis	4.210	.935	4.505	0.393	0.001
Work analysis	<-->	Personal analysis	7.732	1.517	5.098	0.455	0.001
Performance analysis	<-->	Personal analysis	3.326	1.119	2.972	0.249	0.003

Source: primary data

As far as the responses of the female are concerned, the model exposes the relationship between the independent variables and the influence over the mediator dependent variable T & D and through that to the main dependent variable Productivity. From the path analysis diagram related to female, one can note some readings about the relationships and the influences of them over the dependent variables. It is established that the relationship between Performance analysis and Personal analysis is 0.249. The correlation value for Personal analysis and Work analysis is 0.455 and that of Work analysis and Performance analysis seems to be 0.393. All these readings show the relationships among the independent variables; all these readings indicate the average relationships among these and are positively correlated.

The influence of Work analysis over the T & D remains as 0.359 and is the highest of all the influences; Personal analysis influence is 0.241 and the Performance analysis influence over the T & D is 0.121; hence it can be inferred that the Work analysis is the factor which contribute to the T & D thereby it is well understood that the Productivity is well understood that the Productivity is promoted by the Work analysis and less influenced by the Work analysis and less influenced by Personal analysis and Performance analysis. The influence of T & D over Productivity is 0.467 and is positive as far as female are concerned. R² for the T & D is 0.31 and that of Productivity is 0.22; it can be stated that the consolidated influences of the Personal analysis, Work analysis and Performance analysis over the T & D specifically renders 31 percent of influencing effect over the Productivity.

The regression weights of the female responses are shown in the table 4. The table shows the effects of independent variables Personal analysis, Work analysis and Performance analysis toward the Productivity through the T & D which is the mediating dependent variable.

The independent variable Personal analysis shows the estimate as 0.287; SE as 0.088; CR as 3.271 towards T & D which is the mediating dependent variable. The B- value is 0.241 and its corresponding p- value is 0.000 which means that the independent variable Personal analysis influence the Productivity through the mediator dependent variable T & D to 24.1 percent. The Personal analysis shows significant influence over the mediating dependent variable and there is influence of Personal analysis on T & D.

The independent variable Work analysis shows the estimate as 0.269; SE as 0.057; CR as 4.706 towards T & D which is the mediating dependent variable. The B- value is 0.359 and its corresponding p- value is 0.000 which means that the independent variable Work analysis influence the Productivity through the mediator dependent variable T & D to 35.9 percent. The Work analysis shows significant influence over the mediating dependent variable T & D. Baek, (2010) also found that there is influence of Work analysis on T & D.

The independent variable Performance analysis shows the estimate as 0.113; SE as 0.075; CR as -2.807 towards T & D which is the mediating dependent variable. The B- value is 0.121 and its corresponding p- value is 0.007 which means that the independent variable Performance analysis influence the Productivity through the mediator dependent variable T & D to 12.1 percent. The

influence by Performance analysis over the mediating dependent variable T & D is significant. There is influence of Performance analysis on T & D.

The mediating dependent variable T & D Personal analysis shows the estimate as 0.915; SE as 0.141; CR as 6.504 towards T & D which is the mediating dependent variable. The B- value is 0.467 and its corresponding p- value is 0.000 which means that the mediator dependent variable T & D, influence the Productivity through the mediator dependent variable T & D to 46.7 percent. The T & D shows significant influence over the main dependent variable Productivity.

The following table jot out the covariance of the responses of the female. The covariance of male among the independent variables of the study shows the following details. The independent variables namely Personal analysis, Work analysis and Performance analysis have their own interrelationships. The manifestations of their interrelationships are exposed in the table as follows.

The relationship of Work analysis and Performance analysis shows the estimate as 4.210 with the SE of 0.935, the critical ratio is 4.505 and the coefficient of correlation is 0.393 and is positive. Since the p-value is 0.000 it is significant; it can be interpreted that the Work analysis and Performance analysis are significantly related with each other.

The relationship of Work analysis and Personal analysis shows the estimate as 7.732 with the SE of 1.517, the critical ratio is 5.098 and the coefficient of correlation is 0.455 and is positive. Since the p-value is 0.000 it is significant; it can be interpreted that the Work analysis and Personal analysis are significantly related with each other.

The relationship of Performance analysis and Personal analysis shows the estimate as 3.326 with the SE of 1.119, the critical ratio is 2.972 and the coefficient of correlation is 0.249 and is positive. Since the p-value is 0.000 it is significant; it can be interpreted that the Work analysis and Performance analysis are significantly related with each other.

With the readings it can be understood that all the three dependent variables namely Work analysis, Personal analysis and Performance analysis are correlated positively and significantly as with the male.

A Discussion

Based on the multiple group path analysis it can be noted that the relationships between Performance analysis and Personal analysis seems to be higher with the responses of male and female; even though it is so the influence they show towards the T & D is low. Among the three independent variables Work analysis exerts higher influence towards the T & D in both male and female; if so it can be taken for granted that both the gender impart more importance to the Work analysis rather than the Performance analysis and the Personal analysis. The idea that Work analysis is the variable is influencing the Productivity through the T & D as a mediating dependent variable, will lead the producers to produce Personal analysis which are more economical and reachable to the two gender consumers.

Performance analysis is the only dependent variable which shows the negative influence towards the T & D; it can be understood that the total influences received by the T & D is actually pulled down by the Performance analysis beyond from the average relationships with the other two independent variables. As far as the regression weights of female responses are concerned the same variable Performance analysis proves that there is no significant negative influence is rendered by the Performance analysis as an independent variable over the T & D. Since the negative influence is not significant, it need not be given much importance.

Summated influence received by the Productivity is only 26 per cent with female and 29 per cent for male, it can be stated that the etiological contributions of those variables are within 26-29 per

cent the remaining per cent of about 74-71 per cent may be related to exogenous variables; if more variables are considered, the influences received by the Productivity may get a hike.

V Findings

- There are differences in the relationships between the independent variables as perceived by male and female.
- Female responses show that the influence by Performance analysis towards T & D is positive with respect to female and male responses.
- T & D is much influenced by the independent variables; this is felt by the female respondents to show gender differences.
- Similarly the summated influence received by the Productivity is greater with male than with female.
- Through the path analysis it can be noted that the concept of Productivity differs with male and female in total.

Scope for further studies

- Using this model, a specific T & D with specific company can be studied with a larger sample size.
- Advancement in research can be performed by adopting different model

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